

PROBLEM OF SENTENCE STRUCTURE OF CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to find out the problem of sentence structure of deaf children in elementary school. The methods in this study are quantitative and qualitative. The subjects in the study were seven deaf children in grade 5 at one of Surakarta's outstanding private schools. The data collected in this study used oral tests and interviews. The data analysis technique used is data triangulation. The result of this study is the ability to structure the sentence structure of deaf children with normal children differently. Some deaf children have difficulty understanding between subjects, objects, and predicates in placing these elements reversed. As a result, the sentences spoken and written are meaningless, nor the information conveyed and written is not appropriate.

Keywords: children with hearing impairment, special education, the problem of sentence structure.

1. Introduction

Communication skills have begun to be taught informally in the family environment since the child was born. These abilities continue to be developed at the formal education level (School). At the primary education level, children's activeness affects their ability to communicate. Communication skills are included in the language skills that every child must have (Aviana, 2019; Wulandari and Marlina, 2018). Language has specific rules or rules, whether it is about sound, grammar, or sentences. The rules of language are essential to master so that there is an agreement between fellow language users, thus avoiding mistakes in their use (Pradipta and Lesmana, 2019). Some of the language skills taught are speaking and writing skills.

Speaking and writing is a person's ability to pour his thoughts and feelings in oral and written form and as a means to communicate. Writing and speaking are fundamental tools in the teaching and learning process (Wulandari and Marlina, 2018). In speaking or writing, the sentence must have a clear meaning to deliver the message as it should be by following the © 2021 SEAMEO SEN in the language is called grammar which is a grammar with a word that is the largest unit for syntactic administration and the most diminutive word (Pradipta and Lesmana, 2019)

A sentence is a series of arranged words and becomes a whole sentence and have an accurate message. A sentence is a unit of language that has a pattern and contains a particular thought or idea. Patterns in a sentence can be referred to as sentence structures. When communicating, mastery of sentence structure is very important because, with the correct sentence structure, the message can be conveyed well (Siti, 2016; Pradipta and Lesmana, 2019). In speaking and writing skills, proper sentence structure is indispensable in everyday life (Junaidi, 2016; Sunarsih, 2012).

According to Sugihastuti and Saudah (2016), the sentence structure consists of several elements, namely the subject, predicate, object, complement, and description. Still, the sentence must contain at least the subject and predicate. The sentence components must be owned by each sentence and have an appropriate pattern to explain the meaning in a sentence, written, or spoken (Siti, 2016; Haliza et al., 2020). The ability to compose a sentence by the right sentence structure can be taught within the school's scope and outside the school. The power of each child in the preparation of a good and correct sentence structure is undoubtedly different, one of which is for deaf children.

Deafness can be interpreted as a person who has hearing loss and thus experiences obstacles in daily life, but basically, deaf children have an average level of intelligence (Nofiaturrehman, 2018; Sirait et al., 2016; Haliza et al., 2020). The acquisition of language related to language skills in deaf children is influenced by the factors that cause their submission. Submission can occur in prelanguage and post-language periods. Prelingual deafness is a loss of hearing that occurs before speech and language skills develop. In contrast, post-lingual deafness is a loss of hearing that happens after spontaneous speech and language skills (Kirk & Gallagher, 2000). Language problems in deaf children include not much vocabulary, difficulty interpreting words containing expressions, and poor grammar (Rahmah, 2018).

Differences in factors that cause submission certainly affect them in the ability to structure sentences. Still, they must convey messages both verbally and in writing that can be understood by others (Sirait et al., 2016). The direct impact experienced by children who experience hearing barriers is language skills, communicating verbally or verbally (Hidayat, 2015). In general, especially the deaf get a speech skills development at the age of occupying elementary school (Aviana, 2019). Language is an essential skill that must be possessed despite its limitations. As is the case in schools, with a lack of language skills, it is not unlikely that there will be misperceptions that the child will accept. With the proper use of sentence structure, a sentence written will mean it. That's why proper sentence structure is needed in everyday life, including in learning.

In everyday life, deaf children often have difficulty conveying their thoughts and feelings to others. On the contrary, it is also the case for non-deaf children; it is difficult to understand

what the Deaf convey in communicating with non-deaf people. Moreover, the sentence structure used by the Deaf often does not follow the language rules commonly used in communication. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the sentence structure in deaf children in elementary school.

2. Method

This study used a quantitative and qualitatively discrete approach involving seven grade 5 students at one of the outstanding private schools in Surakarta as the subject of research. All five students had hearing loss rates in the moderate category. In communicating daily in the school environment, they use total communication, a combination of sign language and oral language. The data collection techniques used are verbal tests and interviews. The data analysis technique used is a qualitative descriptive narrative. The criteria in the assessment of verbal tests and interviews are as follows:

1. Simple sentence pattern, including S-P-O elements (subject, predicate, object)
2. Simple and complementary sentence patterns, including elements of S-P-O-Pel (Subject, predicate, object, and complement)
3. Simple sentence patterns and captions, including elements of S-P-O-Ket (Subject, predicate, object, and description)

Each sentence structure used criteria very well, well, less, and very less (SB, B, C, K, SK).

SB : describe that the child can communicate by using a complete sentence structure pattern appropriately. A quantitative score between 81 – 100.

B : describe that the child can communicate by using a complete pattern of sentence structure but still not precise or inconsistent. The quantitative score between 61 – 80.

C : describe that the child can communicate using incomplete and inconsistent sentence structure patterns but can still be understood. Kuantutatuf score between 41 – 60

K : describe that the child in question can sometimes communicate using a pattern of sentence structure but is incomplete and inconsistent, and difficult to understand. The quantitative score between 21 - 40

SK : describe that the child is no longer able to communicate by using a complete sentence structure pattern appropriately or sentences is not clear. His quantitative score is 20 and under from this.

Based on the findings, recommendations are prepared in guidance as necessary through remedial teaching, more intensive guidance through corrective and training, and advice with special programs. In addition, the third group needs to be created an individual language learning program.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Result

Table 1. Mastery of sentence structure in research subjects

No	Subject	Mastery of sentence structure	Assessment Results	Quantitative score	Category
1	NT	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simple sentence pattern 2. Simple sentence pattern plus complement 3. Simple sentence pattern plus description 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The sentence structure of the child is not patterned. 2. The sentence structure of the child is not patterned. 3. The sentence structure of the child is not patterned. 	15	Very less
2	ZH	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simple sentence pattern 2. Simple sentence pattern plus complement 3. Simple sentence pattern plus description 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The sentence of the child is only a patterned subject. Therefore, there is no Predicate and Object element/there is only one sentence element in the correct position. 2. The sentence of the child is only a patterned subject. There is no Predicate and Complement element, or there is only one sentence element in the correct position. 3. The sentence of the child is only a patterned subject. There is no Predicate, Object and Description element, or there is only one sentence element in the correct position. 	26,6	Less
3	RN	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simple sentence pattern 2. Simple sentence pattern plus complement 3. Simple sentence pattern plus description 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The sentence of the child is only a patterned subject. Therefore, there is no Predicate and Object element/there is only one sentence element in the correct position. 2. The sentence of the child is only a patterned subject. For example, there is no Predicate and Complement element, or there is only one sentence element in the correct position. 3. The sentence of the child is only a patterned subject. For example, there is no Predicate, Object and Description element, or there is only one sentence element in the correct 	26,6	Less

			position.		
4	ST	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simple sentence pattern 2. Simple sentence pattern plus complement 3. Simple sentence pattern plus description 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The sentence structure of the child is not patterned. 2. The sentence structure of the child is not patterned. 3. The sentence structure of the child is not patterned. 	5	Very less
5	ZL	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simple sentence pattern 2. Simple sentence pattern plus complement 3. Simple sentence pattern plus description 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The sentence of the child is only a patterned subject. Therefore, there is no Predicate and Object element/there is only one sentence element in the correct position. 2. The sentence of the child is only a patterned subject. For example, there is no Predicate and Complement element, or there is only one sentence element in the correct position. 3. The sentence of the child is only a patterned subject. There is no Predicate, Object and Description element, or there is only one sentence element in the correct position. 	21,6	Less
6	AD	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simple sentence pattern 2. Simple sentence pattern plus complement 3. Simple sentence pattern plus description 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Children's sentences are predicate-object patterned only. Therefore, there is no Subject element/there are only two elements of the sentence in the correct position. 2. The child sentence is only subject-predicate patterned, or there are only two elements of the sentence in the correct position. 3. The child sentence is the only subject-predicate pattern, or there are only two elements of the sentence in the correct position. 	53,3	Enough
7	RD	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simple sentence pattern 2. Simple sentence 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. S-P-O patterned but inconsistent child sentences 	70	Good

		pattern plus complement 3. Simple sentence pattern plus description	2. Subject-Predicate-Object patterned child sentences. Occasionally it comes with complementary elements in the correct position. 3. Subject-Predicate-Object patterned child sentences. There are Subject, Predicate, Object, and Description elements in the correct but inconsistent position.		
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Table 2. Summary of Sentence Structure Mastery Assessment Results in Research Subjects

No	Name (Initial)	Value	Information
1	NT	15	Very low
2	ZH	26,6	Low
3	RN	26,6	Low
4	ST	5	Very low
5	ZL	21,6	Low
6	AD	53,3	Enough
7	RD	70	Good
Average		31,15	Low

Based on these results, it can be known that there are 2 (two) subjects with very little mastery of sentence structure, 3 (three) subjects including fewer categories, and 1 (one) subject with good types, and 1 (one) subject with a good type. Of the seven subjects, most or 5 (five) children are less and significantly less or if made a percentage reaches 70.7%. Only 2 (two) subjects fall into the category of sufficient and good, or if made, a percentage reaches 29.3%.

3.2. Discussion

This finding illustrates that in grade V elementary school deaf students with moderate impairment rate, it turns out that most of them (70.7%) experiencing real language difficulties is characterized by the inability to communicate using the standard and correct sentence structure pattern, i.e. the simple pattern of S-P-O or S-P-O-Pel. or S-P-O-Pel-Ket. These findings illustrate that language learning in deaf children at the elementary level has not been effective. Failure in language learning at the elementary level will greatly affect the mastery of knowledge in other subjects, either at the elementary level or the development of education at the next level. Indeed, they need more intensive guidance, remedial learning, and exceptional guidance outside of learning hours, especially language practice activities using the correct sentence structure. Language delays due to hearing impairment require all components of the school, especially teachers, to be more intensive in providing language learning materials, especially at the elementary school level.

The child's understanding of the elements of sentence structure is still low. For example, some children still have a misconception between "Subject", "Object", and "Predicate" by placing the element upside down. Some children only understand the concept of "Subject". This can cause sentences that are spoken and written to be meaningless or information submitted and written inappropriately. So it can lead to hampered communication of children with others. Based on observations, daily sentences in children used in the learning process and to communicate with others are not patterned. In composing a sentence, the pattern of children's sentences is still often reversed, both in writing and verbally. For example, when the child is working on making a sentence that should be "I go to school with my father" to "school goes with the father". It also has an impact on their ability to absorb the information provided. The ability of deaf children in composing sentence structures is different from normal children. In line with the study results, Hanafi et al. (2016) and Nofiaturrehman (2018) explained that deaf sentences have the wrong syntax structure. There is the use and addition of inappropriate words in one sentence, and the reduction of the word should be. In learning activities, children copywriting more often than participate directly. This causes the child's ability to compose the sentence structure will not to develop so that the design of the sentence spoken or written by the child himself is still ambiguous. Based on the research results from Pradipta and Lesmana (2019), the ability of deaf children in grade IX SMPLB in composing simple sentences is still unstructured and difficult to understand the meaning.

Language functions as a vehicle to make communication contacts, express feelings, needs, desires, informers, and gain deep knowledge. If language and speaking skills are lacking, it will cause related problems (Aviana, 2019; Christine, 2020). Furthermore, Aviana (2019) added that if experiencing barriers in language and speech will also affect other aspects of life, including auditive perceptions, intellectual knowledge, emotions, parents and society, vocational, social, and education. The form of communication that deaf children have begins to take shape when they run a series of learning and training of language and speaking skills routinely provided by teachers in the school and parents and surrounding areas. Their ability, in general, makes communicating in the form of sign language by optimizing nonverbal forms of communication through gestures, face, eyes, touch, and follow the movement of lips. However, this resulted in the sentence structure used by the child is still ambiguous.

Writing this ambiguous sentence structure certainly has another impact on the child. When the child is still writing with a sentence structure that does not fit the correct pattern, it will impact the ability to write higher levels, such as writing a report, description, etc. The habit of writing sentences with ambiguous sentence structure can also cause difficulties in children in conveying information when communicating and can lead to low learning achievements of children (Wulandari and Marlina, 2018). The learning process must use communication, and if the sentence structure of the child is ambiguous, then it is not impossible that there can be misunderstandings in the learning process. Therefore, deaf children must have oral and written skills with the correct sentence structure to not cause other problems.

The language skills of deaf children are impaired. This is due to the lack of information that children receive through the sense of hearing, while language development is closely related to hearing ability (Aviana, 2019; Junaidi, 2016). Language and speech are the results of the impersonation process. The lack of information received causes deaf children to experience speech delays and limited word preservation. The limitations of preserving the word affect the child's language skills, which cause the child to have difficulty communicating, understanding the information received and interpreting figurative language and abstract words (Siti, 2016;

Pradipta and Lesmana, 2019; Haliza et al., 2020). Children who experience language barriers will encounter barriers to communicating their thoughts more fully (Lyster, 2003). In the development of language and speech, deaf children have difficulty in the stage of imitating. At the time of imitating deaf children was limited to visual, namely motion and gestures. Further language development in deaf children requires unique and intensive coaching, following submission and other abilities.

In line with Hernawati (2007) findings, submission resulted in the development of children's language is hampered. Children's speech is impaired due to the limitations of word preservation. These language barriers also result in obstacles in communication and social interaction of children with others. At the same time, the use of language is essential because language contains an idea or purpose so that it is needed in daily life. A language is a communication tool used in the family environment, the community, and the school environment. In addition, language is also used in learning in schools, where it fulfils the child's right to obtain an education. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the ability of children in language, mainly to compose sentences by the correct sentence structure.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research conducted, all research subjects have problems using sentence structures that are still ambiguous in communicating both verbally and in writing. More than (70.1%) category deaf people have issues forming sentences that require the use of Subject-Predicate-Object-Complicated-Description (S-P-O-PeI-Ket) sentence structure. And only about (29.9%) have mastery of the approaching sentence structure precisely. In addition, subjects experience concept errors in simple sentence elements, such as concept errors in the placement of Subjects, Predicates and Objects, and Appendages and Captions due to the impact of their submission. Therefore, it takes an effort to improve the ability of the Deaf in language, mainly to compose sentences by the correct sentence structure. Based on these findings, it is recommended that language learning for the Deaf be intensified, remedial teaching is carried out, and guidance outside of learning hours, especially for proper language practice exercises, can be done in schools. Furthermore, the number of hours of Bahasa Indonesia lessons at SLB Tunarungu needs to be reviewed according to the needs of the Deaf.

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